

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Zuhriddinov Hayotbek Qaxramonjon o'g'li

**LEARNING THE SKILLS OF ERGONOMIC KNOWLEDGE IN PRODUCTION
THROUGH DIGITALIZATION**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2022/DEKABR

